

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF VAPORIZATION OF MONO-COMPONENT FUEL DROPLETS IN A GAS TURBINE ENGINE

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of variation of radius and the surface temperature of the fuel droplets in sprays of combustion chambers in gas turbines is studied. Differential equation of first order, relating surface temperature, radius and time is derived and solved by finite difference method (FDM). Finite difference method is continued until the droplet reaches its flash point temperature at the specified combustion chamber conditions i.e., 8000c and 12 bar. The Process is repeated for three monocomponent fuels n-Butanol, n-Heptane, Ethanol. Generalized parabolic equations are derived for all the six fuels which give the temporal variations of fuel droplet surface temperature and droplet radius, using which disintegration radius and critical time of any fuel droplet can be known. To check the validity of the equations the analysis is carried out for three other fuels Methanol, 1-Propanol and n-Octane using FDM and the results are compared to those obtained from the developed equations.

Keywords: Modelling of Droplet, Droplet Models, Mono-component fuel, Non-Dimensionalizing, Finite Difference Method (FDM), Surface Temperature, Disintegrating Radius, Critical Time.

Description

2.1 Formulation

The energy balance applied to a single fuels droplet is - available energy at an instant is equal to the sum of heat transferred by convection and heat transferred by radiation between the droplet and the surrounding ambient gas which is at higher temperature than that of the droplet. The droplet initial temperature is considered to be at room temperature. The effect of conduction through the droplet is considered to be negligible when compared with the effects of convection and radiation. The whole process is taken as transient and derivation is carried out as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} [mc_p(T - T_o)] = h_{conv}[T_g - T]A + \varepsilon c_o A [T_g^4 - T^4]$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} [mc_p(T - T_o)] = \text{Available energy at an instant}$$

$$h_{conv}[T_g - T]A = \text{Heat transferred by convection}$$

$$\varepsilon c_o A [T_g^4 - T^4] = \text{Heat transferred by radiation}$$

The respective formulae for mass and area are substituted in the given energy balance equation.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi R^2 \rho c_p (T - T_o) \right] = h_{conv} [T_g - T] * 4\pi R^2 + \varepsilon c_o * 4\pi R^2 * [T_g^4 - T^4] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dR^*}{dFo} * \frac{3}{R^*} (T^* - T_o^*) + \frac{dT^*}{dFo} = \frac{3\pi h}{R^*} (1 - T^*) + \frac{3\pi \varepsilon}{R^*} (1 - T^{*4}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dT^*}{dFo} = \frac{3\pi h}{R^*} (1 - T^*) + \frac{3\pi \varepsilon}{R^*} (1 - T^{*4}) - \frac{dR^*}{dFo} * \frac{3}{R^*} (T^* - T_o^*) \quad (3)$$

Mass of droplet available at any instant = mass of the droplet at interface + mass of the surrounding.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi R^2 \rho \right] = -h_m [\rho_i - \rho_\infty] * 4\pi R^2 \quad (4)$$

$$h_m = \text{mass transfer coefficient} \frac{m}{s}$$

ρ_i = density of droplet at interface

ρ_∞ = density of fuel droplet far away from the interface

$$\pi_m = \frac{h_m}{\alpha_l \rho_l} * \frac{P_\infty}{R_g T_g} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dR^*}{dFo} = -\pi_m \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dR^*}{dFo} = -\pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dT^*}{dFo} = \frac{3\pi h}{R^*} (1 - T^*) + \frac{3\pi \varepsilon}{R^*} (1 - T^{*4}) + \pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] * \frac{3}{R^*} (T^* - T_o^*) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dT^*}{dR^*} = \frac{\frac{3\pi h}{R^*} (1 - T^*) + \frac{3\pi \varepsilon}{R^*} (1 - T^{*4}) + \pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] * \frac{3}{R^*} (T^* - T_o^*)}{-\pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right]} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dR^*}{dFo} = -\pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{dT^*}{dFo} = \frac{3\pi h}{R^*} (1 - T^*) + \frac{3\pi \varepsilon}{R^*} (1 - T^{*4}) + \pi_h * \beta \left[\frac{1 - T^*}{T^*} \right] * \frac{3}{R^*} (T^* - T_o^*) \quad (11)$$

2.1 Results and discussions

The graphs for dimensionless temperature and dimensionless radius, Fourier number and dimensionless radius are plotted for all the six fuels namely n-Butanol, Acetone, Ethanol, n-Heptane, 3-Pentanone and n-Decane. All the critical time values and critical radius values are plotted on order to get the common equation. The obtained equation is a fifth order polynomial. And all dimensionless temperature values and dimensionless radius values are plotted whose resultant equation is a third degree polynomial. With these two equations for the fuels with flash point temperature in the range of 300c to 1200c and at the mentioned combustion chamber conditions the critical parameters can be easily calculated by trial and error method or direct calculation of roots. For a monocomponent fuel droplet the variation of all the three parameters time, temperature and radius are parabolic in nature.

Fuel Name	Fourier Number	Flash point	Critical time	Critical radius	Alpha $10^{-8} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$
n-Butanol	0.0013	76	0.099303	0.002817	10.3882
Ethanol	0.0005	44.126	0.04775	0.002942	9.66053
n-Heptane	0.0013	82.367	0.120902	0.002721	7.9628

Table 1 Comparison of critical time and Critical radius

Fig 1 Variation Temperature with time

Figure 2 Variation of Temperature with Fourier number

Fig 3 Variation of dimensionless radius with Fo

Fig 4 Variation of Dimensionless Temperature with Dimensionless radius

Critical time is more for the fuel with high flash point temperature. . The fuels with least disintegration time show almost linear behaviour in graph but the exact results are possible only with quadratic equations since all the governing differential equations are of single order hence the functions will be definitely polynomials of degree two.

Both the graphs are almost linear and show similar behaviour, this depicts that the model followed in the work are almost near to approximations. The graphs are with minimal deviation when shown along with ideal values given by Elwardany (2012).

Fig 5 Comparison of present analysis with experimental data given by Elwardany (2012)

Fig 6 Comparison of present analysis with experimental data given by Elwardany (2012)

All the relations are obtained in parabolic or quadratic form which are compatible with the standard one given for parabolic temperature profile. The same process can be carried out for bi component and multi component fuel droplets. For mono component fuel droplets, the temperature of the fuel droplet is assumed to be constant throughout evaporation process. And the phenomenon of conductivity and breakup within the fuel droplet are assumed to be negligible. With the obtained equation the time period for evaporation of a specific fuel droplet can be easily calculated if the specified constants are known. These constants vary for each fuel depending upon their properties such as thermal conductivity of liquid and vapour of the fuel, Thermal Diffusion, specific density of liquid and vapour phase, Specific heats of liquid and vapour fuel, boiling point and flash point of the fuels and finally the ambient conditions maintained inside the combustion chamber.

Final equations

$$T^* = A1R^{*2} + B1R^* + C1$$

$$R^* = A2Fo^2 + B2 Fo + C2$$

$$T^* = A3Fo^2 + B3 Fo + C3$$

Table 2 Coefficients of all the three equations of all the fuels

<i>Fuel Name</i>	<i>A1</i>	<i>B1</i>	<i>C1</i>	<i>A2</i>	<i>B2</i>	<i>C2</i>	<i>A3</i>	<i>B3</i>	<i>C3</i>
n-Butanol	2.9149	-6.5671	3.9993	4305.9	-52.51	1	2517.7	38.989	0.3471
Ethanol	2.9829	-6.8173	4.1814	3003.1	-40.453	1	3689.3	34.977	0.347
n-Heptane	1.9404	-4.374	2.7808	7313.5	-80.963	1	4975.3	41.054	0.3471

The common equation for estimating the disintegration radius and critical time are as follows:

$$R^* = 36.185T^{*3} - 39.668T^{*2} + 13.355T^* - 0.37$$

$$R = 736.76t^5 - 332.26t^4 + 54.883t^3 - 4.0654t^2 + 0.1276t + 0.0017$$

Where T* is dimensionless temperature, R* is dimensionless radius and t is critical time. The above mentioned equations are valid for the flash point temperature range from 30⁰C to 130⁰C. The mean error of the equations lies in the range of 0.02 to 0.04 when examined for all the given fuels. Resultant equations are examined for few of the standard fuels. Such as methanol, propanol and octane.

3. Conclusions

- Governing differential equations for dimensionless radius, dimensionless temperature and Fourier number are obtained.
- Variation of critical parameters i.e., radius, temperature and time during disintegration are calculated for all the fuels viz., n-Butanol, Ethanol, n-Heptane, and the pertinent graphs are plotted.
- The values obtained from the present work are compared with those given by Elwardany (mentioned in literature) by plotting comparative graphs and they are found to conform with each other.
- Common equation for disintegration radius and critical time is obtained for all the six fuels considered. The mean error of the values obtained from the equation when compared to the procedural values is found to be in the range of -0.02201 to 0.03024.
- The equation obtained is valid for the mono-component fuels whose flash point temperature lies in the range of 30 °C to 120 °C at the specified combustion conditions.